

Ionic Selectivity in Biological Systems

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Ion binding to biological surfaces is discussed with special reference to the authors' previous work on binding of Ca^{++} and of alkali-metal ions to serum lipoproteins. The very low concentration of CaCl_2 required for charge reversal of low density lipoprotein was interpreted to be due to exposed phospholipid groups on the surface of the lipoprotein. The binding of alkali metal ions was studied in terms of their effects on the binding of a fluorescent probe. The results indicated that while Li^+ was bound to the greatest extent, its affinity for binding was the least. The phenomena of charge reversal and of the higher binding capacity of Li^+ would be in keeping with binding in the Stern Layer of nonhydrated ions ; the affinity sequence is best explained by the theory of Eisenman assuming a low field strength of the phospholipid phosphate, with dehydration energy being the determining factor.

BIOLICAL systems are characterised by marked specificities, ionic specificity being among them.

Not only is the physiological milieu, for example, of a certain ionic strength (~ 0.15), but its ionic composition is very important for normal physiological function. Cells maintain a certain ionic composition, very often different from their surroundings. Pump mechanisms present on the cell membranes allow the flux of one ion in preference to others. Enzymes very often require specific ions for their action. In a sense the biological system is an ion binding, or ion exchange system *par excellence*.

Based on the effects of different ions on properties like solubility of hydrophilic colloids, sequences known as Hofmeister or lyotropic series can be written for anions :

and for cations :

the series representing decreasing efficiency of "salting out"¹. While the sequence $\text{Cs}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ is observed in many phenomena involving alkali metal cations, it was discovered early that the sequence is not sacrosanct ; the reverse sequence as well as a number of transitional ones in between the two extremes have been observed ; of the total number of permutations of five alkali metal ions only eleven have been found in biological and non-biological systems^{2,3}. Biological systems do not hold any monopoly for any particular sequence.

Theories about the origin of ionic specificities have been advanced over many decades. Electrochemical and electrokinetic aspects of ion-binding and ion exchange were studied by colloid chemists with great enthusiasm. As early as in 1921 Mukherjee⁴ proposed that a part of the counterions of a charged surface may be electrochemically bound or adsorbed to the surface ionic groups, a picture later to be modified as the "Stern layer"⁵. In 1932 Jenny⁶ proposed that alkali metal ionic sequences other than "normal" (i.e. the Hofmeister) are due to dehydration of cations. Bungenberg de Jong⁷ studied ionic specificities in a number of organic colloids with carboxyl, phosphate and sulphate ionic groups. The specificities were determined in terms of the minimum concentration of salt (cation) required to reverse the charge on these colloid particles from negative to positive, as revealed by electrophoresis. Charge reversal spectra of ions were established characteristic of different anionic groups.

Our experiments concern ionic specificities for certain serum lipoproteins which carry lipids such as triglycerides, phospholipids and cholesterol in blood. The low density lipoprotein (LDL) has been implicated in the development of atherosclerosis ; ionic interaction of LDL with polyanionic mucopolysaccharides of arterial wall has been suggested as important in the process. Our interest has been to characterize the surface groups of lipoprotein and their ionic preferences.

Charge reversal of low density lipoprotein by Ca^{++} :

Electrophoresis of LDL and of albumin was performed in gels of agarose or agar as supporting

material. The basal solution was tris buffer of pH 6.8 and ionic strength 0.005. Experimental buffers contained CaCl_2 or NaCl in addition. Gels (0.6%) were cast using such solutions. During electrophoresis in the gels, along with LDL and albumin a sample of Vit B_{12} was run as a marker for electroendosmosis and thus of the charge of the gel material: agarose or agar. The correction for the effect of gel on electrophoretic mobility has been discussed previously⁹. The results showed that the lipoprotein LDL which had a net negative charge in the control solution became positive above a concentration of about 15 mM CaCl_2 . Charge reversal did not occur even in 0.15M NaCl . Furthermore, neither agar, agarose or albumin showed charge reversal at the above concentration of Ca^{++} showing the presence of specific groups on LDL. The charge reversal concentration of Ca^{++} for LDL has been compared in Table I with those for several known surface groups as determined by Bungenberg de Jong⁷. On the basis of these values it was suggested that phospholipid head groups are exposed on the surface of LDL. This was later confirmed by us using the enzyme Phospholipase D¹⁰. Specificities with respect to alkali metal ions could not be studied by this method.

TABLE I

CHARGE REVERSAL CONCENTRATION (C. R. C.) of CaCl_2		
Colloid type		C.R.C. (M)
Carboxylate*	pectinate	1.2
Sulphate *	agar	6.3
Phosphate *	lecithin (+ cholesterol)	1.7×10^{-2}
	LDL	1.5×10^{-3}

* Estimated from figures of Ref. 7.

Effect of ions on the binding of ANS to LDL¹¹ :

The fluorescent probe ANS (1-anilino 8-naphthalene sulphoate) has been used as a probe for hydrophobic regions on the surfaces of proteins and membranes. On binding, the fluorescence increases and the increase may be used to quantitate the binding. The extent and affinity of the binding of ANS to different lipoproteins have been reported by us^{11,12}. The conclusion of the studies has been that ANS binds to the phospholipid moieties of the lipoprotein surface. Binding of ANS to low and high density lipoproteins (LDL and HDL) was studied in presence of different ions. Details of the procedure and results have been published (*loc. cit.*). Binding increased with increase in salt concentration in the medium; the concentration of Ca^{++} required to achieve a given binding was less than 10 per cent of the concentration of NaCl needed for the same extent of ANS binding or of the fluorescence enhancement.

Binding of a ligand L to a protein P may be described by the equation, sometimes called Klotz equation¹³ :

$$\frac{P}{xL_0} = \frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{xK_a(L_0 - xL_0)}$$

where n is the number of binding sites per molecule of the protein, L_0 the total concentration of the ligand, x the fraction of ligand bound and K_a the association constant for the protein-ligand binding. As mentioned earlier, x is proportional to ΔF , the increase in fluorescence on binding.

Double reciprocal plots of ΔF and ligand concentration ($L_0 - xL_0$) can be used to get a number of useful information. For example, at a particular ligand concentration, if the fluorescence is measured as a function of increasing lipoprotein concentration, the intercept of a double reciprocal plot using the concentration of lipoprotein gives the fluorescence when all the ligand is bound i.e. of the intrinsic fluorescence of the bound ligand. The intrinsic fluorescence of bound ANS was found to be independent of the nature or the concentration of the salt present in the medium. Any effect of salt on fluorescence would therefore be due to differences in the extent of binding.

Increased binding of the ANS anion in presence of salt has suggested to be due to the neutralisation of the phospholipid phosphate group by the bound cation and therefore may be used to determine cation binding to phospholipid head groups. Thus, if salt concentration is studied as the independent variable, the double reciprocal plots of ΔF (at a constant ANS and lipoprotein concentration) and salt concentration may indicate the extent of salt binding as affecting the binding of ANS. The data obtained in presence of increasing NaCl , KCl , LiCl and CsCl showed that binding of ANS at any concentration of the salts increased in the series $\text{Cs}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Li}^+$. Analysis of the data by double reciprocal plots showed however that the increased binding was related to increase in the number of binding sites; in fact, the affinities of the cations for lipoproteins were shown to decrease in the series $\text{Cs}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$. This is similar to the findings of Gomperts *et al.*¹⁴ for ANS binding to microsomal membranes and those of Träuble on phospholipid vesicles in water¹⁵.

The immediate implication of these results is that evidence of increase in binding under a given circumstance does not necessarily mean an increase in affinity. The extent of binding should be analysed in terms of the affinity and the capacity factors for binding. The affinity K_a alone should be used in discussion on specificity of ion binding, although some insight into the mechanisms involved may be derived from a comparison of the capacity values. As the cation binding in the above experiments was not determined directly but rather derived indirectly from measurements of ANS binding, direct determination of ion binding to such surfaces should be undertaken to confirm the validity of the above approach.

Discussion

The affinity is the key parameter for comparing ion selectivity. The selectivity coefficient, $K_{A/B}$, for exchange of a cation A for another B, has been defined in terms of an equilibrium

where a bar signifies the cation bound, the other being free in solution. One writes in terms of activities of the different species :

$$K_{A/B} = \frac{(A)(\bar{B})}{(\bar{A})(B)}$$

For the exchange process, the affinity or the standard free energy is given by

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{A/B}$$

One way to determine such affinity is to use an E.M.F. cell working on the exchange reaction. This was proposed by Marshall¹⁶, and a cell using plugs of mont-morrillonite was used by Mukherjee and Marshall¹⁷ to determine the energies of K^+/Na^+ and of $\frac{Ca^{++}}{2}/K^+$ exchange. The values obtained

were 227 cal/mole for the former and 695 cal/mole for the latter. For homoionic surfaces, the affinity of exchange was shown to be equal to the differences in the standard free energy of the simple processes : binding of B and binding of A.

Theories of ion selectivity historically dwelt on the sequence for alkali metal cations $Cs > Rb > K > Na > Li$ the so-called "normal" sequence. Since this is the order expected for electrostatic interaction that can be calculated using the hydrated radii of the cations, this remained a point of reference for looking at other sequences as though generated by gradual stripping of the hydration layer of one or the other ion. Bungenberg de Jong⁷ proposed that different cationic selectivity sequences are obtained for anions of different polarizability. Polarizability of different anions and of water was assumed to be in the order :

phosphate > carboxylate > water > sulfate.

For an anionic exchange site more polarizable than water, cation-site interaction will be more important than cation-water interaction, and the sequence will be according to the non-hydrated radii of the cations. For a site less polarizable than water, the normal sequence will be obtained. In the early theories, the transition sequences were suggested to be due to a stripping of the hydration shell of the alkali metal cations starting from Li^+ , the most hydrated of them. Incorrect transition sequences were predicted, the reversal generally starting at the Cs^+ end and not at the Li^+ end³.

Ling¹⁸ attempted to apply statistical thermody-

namical methods to calculate the interaction between an anion and a cation in a number of configurations with different numbers of water molecules between the two ions. All types of electrostatic interactions (Coulomb to London) as well as Born repulsion were included in these calculations. Variation of the acid strength of the group by induction effect was introduced as an important parameter and was shown in his calculations to be able to give rise to different alkali ion selectivity sequences. While the theory has great appeal to biochemists being relevant for carboxyl groups of proteins, the calculations were done only for linear (i.e. one dimensional) configurations. Furthermore, the theory was unable to predict the exact types of inversions in the sequences.

The currently accepted theory which seems to have correctly predicted all the observed sequences for alkali metal ions, is due to Eisenman². Eisenman considered the Coulombic free energy of interaction between the two ions, as well as the energy of hydration of the cations. The reference point is not the hydrated radius of the cation. Key in dictating selectivity in this theory is the field strength of the anion, dependent on its radius. For an anion of small radius, the field strength would be high, the Coulombic interaction will be more important (in terms of the magnitude) than the hydration energy, and the anion will prefer in the sequence $Li^+ > Na^+ > K^+ > Cs^+$. On the other hand, if the anion is large and of low field strength, dehydration energies will be of importance in selectivity and the sequence of preference will be $Cs^+ > K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$. Intermediate field strengths generate transition sequences as experimentally observed. Other factors, such as accessibility of the site to water, have been considered in so far as they would attenuate the selectivity. The magnitude of the exchange energy in absence of water was rather high in these calculations. The energy for K/Na exchange determined by Mukherjee and Marshall was much smaller (200 cal/mole). This order of magnitude is approached in Eisenman's model when water is present in the region of binding².

In case of phospholipid head groups as on biological membranes and lipoprotein, the Zwitterionic group phosphatidyl choline is the predominant one, the phosphate negative charge being between the buried hydrophobic group and the positively charged choline group. It is possible that a smaller ion like Li^+ can have a greater access to these anionic groups than the others ; this would explain why for the type of surface that obtains in lipoproteins, the binding capacity may be different for different cations. However, as suggested by Gomperts *et al.*⁴¹ the higher dehydration energy for the smaller ion would tend to make its overall affinity of binding lower thus explaining the sequence of affinities $Cs^+ > K^+ > Na^+ > Li^+$.

Two points are worth mentioning in support of this contention. First, the counterions adsorbed in

the Stern layer⁵ are so close to the surface that the finite size of the ions becomes an important factor and it is possible that the maximum coverage will depend on ionic size. Secondly, Gomperts *et al.*¹⁴ studied the binding of the ions as a function of temperature and calculated the enthalpy and entropy for the process; the values indicate the binding to be entropy driven, the entropy change presumably due to the breakdown of the ordered structure of water around the ions.

Ion exchange, in practice, involves a separate phase. The ions associated with the exchanger phase may be more than what constitute the Stern layer. The internal space of this phase is like the inside of a crosslinked swollen gel and has the capacity of holding a good bit of the diffuse layer. Secondly, natural ion-exchangers are probably always heterogeneous, as illustrated by the studies of Mukherjee and Ghosh¹⁹. As reviewed by Reichenberg²⁰, the effects of such factors as heterogeneity, crystallographic structure, change-spacing, cross linking, Donnan effect and swelling on the ion-exchange phenomena could be quite complicated. However, for a proper understanding of the specificities, it is important to be able to sort out the affinity of binding from the other complicating factors.

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